

Effects of Physical Therapy Combined with Footwear Modifications on Cadence, Stride Length and Speed in Patients with Knee Osteoarthritis. (A Randomized Clinical Trial)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 17, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: October 18, 2022</p>	<p><i>Background: People who have osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee are frequently required to wear shoes that reduce the knee's adduction moment. There is a lack of evidence on how footwear adjustments along with physiotherapy treatment might enhance spatiotemporal gait characteristics in knee OA patients. Objectives: To determine the variation in the effect of two types of footwear modifications along with physiotherapy treatment on gait characteristics of patients with knee Osteoarthritis.</i></p> <p><i>Methodology: 60 individuals with osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee were randomly assigned to two experimental groups. Group A (n=30) underwent conventional Physical therapy treatment and footwear adjustment as Lateral Heel Wedge with Medial arch support while group B (n=30) received conventional physiotherapy treatment and footwear adjustment as Lateral Heel Wedge only. Fast cadence, Speed and stride length were evaluated at baseline as well as 8th, 16th and 24th week of treatment. Data was analyzed by Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28. Unstandardized beta coefficients with 95% confidence intervals were provided to aid in the interpretation of the data. Data was presented as mean \pm, and frequency while to find out the association of cadence speed and stride length with both group's treatment protocol.</i></p> <p><i>Results: Both groups were not significantly different at the baseline. Of the spatiotemporal gait characteristics, the fast cadence statistically increased by the 8th week for both groups, with a non-significant difference indicated as $p=0.59$. P-values of 0.03 at 16th week and 0.007 at 24th week were observed for between-group analysis, with Group A showing better improvement. Fast stride length of both groups improved significantly but more in group A after 8th week ($p=0.01$), 16th week ($p=0.013$) and 24th week ($p=0.05$) Fast speed was increased in all three intervals for both groups having significant correlation ($p=0.20, 0.03, 0.009$). But better results in patients using footwear with medial arch support.</i></p> <p><i>Conclusion: There was significant association found between physical therapy intervention and both types of footwear modification in terms of improving spatiotemporal gait characteristics, but the statistics showed that the group with Lateral heel wedge with Medial arch support presented with better improvements in these parameters.</i></p>
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Introduction

Osteoarthritis is the most prevalent cause of disability. The medial compartment of knee is mostly involved in OA. (1) Patients with knee OA present with stiffness, pain, and a loss in range of joint motion. (2) As knee is weight-bearing joint of body and is involved in locomotion, gait is most affected by OA of knee. Majority of studies reported that the majorly affected gait parameters are step and stride length, cadence, and speed. Research has frequently shown that, as compared to healthy control subjects, patients with knee OA has less walking speed, short stride length and lengthy stance. Reducing walking pace and stride length was an adaptive way to minimize pain as it reduces adduction moments of knee. (3, 4) Moreover, Debi et al., 2009 found that knee osteoarthritis patients of both genders walk at a similar speed with matching movement patterns, cadences and step lengths. (5) Marlene et. al found that gait parameters in individuals with osteoarthritis of the knee, all noticeably showed a better outcome than controls following physical therapy treatment. (6) Numerous studies have demonstrated that modifying the footwear can lessen lateral knee strain, ligaments' tension, pain, and improve functionality in those with mild to moderate OA of the medial tibiofemoral compartment. Though the usage of lateral heel wedges has brought attention, there is much disagreement in the studies over its ability to effectively reduce discomfort and functional

limitations.(7)Remarkably, adding a medial arch to the lateral wedge insole enhanced health-related outcomes on a clinical basis by minimizing the adduction moment of the knee even further.(8)But there is a lack of evidence on how footwear modifications and physiotherapy treatment improve spatiotemporal gait parameters in patients with knee OA. Therefore, the aim of this study was to study the effects of two types of footwear modifications along with physical therapy treatment on the spatiotemporal gait parameters (Stride length, speed and cadence) of individuals with knee OA.

Methodology

In this Randomized Clinical Trial (RCT),60 participants diagnosed with OA were randomized into two experimental groups (A and B) with a sample size of 30 in each group.The study was approved by Research Ethical Committee, Institutional Review Board and Board of Advanced Studies and Research Isra University, Islamabad Pakistan. The protocol of study was registered on National Library of Medicine (**NCT04536519**). Sampling of subjects was done using probability convenient purposive sampling technique. Randomization was done using the lottery method. Participants who met the following inclusion criteria were included in the sample: Individuals 50 years of age or older, have been diagnosed with knee osteoarthritis on a clinical and radiographic basis, have had knee pain for at least one month with an intensity of at least 4, fall between grades 2-3 on the Kellgren-Lawrence Classification System for knee osteoarthritis, have a BMI between 22 and 25 kg/m², and gave consent to participate in the study of their own free will and with a signed consent form. Exclusion criteria for the sample were: Patients with systemic arthritic disease, severe co-morbidities or serious medical conditions, systemic disease causing dependent edema, making it difficult to wear footwear in the last month, patients with known histories of knee trauma, patients undergoing knee or lower limb surgery for fracture or arthroplasty, patients receiving steroid-based intra-articular injection or physiotherapy treatment in the last six months, patients receiving lidocaine intra-articular injection in the last month.

The baseline data was taken which included gait parametric measures. The fast-walking speed was measured by 2-Minute Walk Test (2MWT) (9)which was performed over a 50-feet out-and-back path. The patients were instructed to walk at their fast pace and cover as much distance as possible in 2 minutes. The patients were positioned a few steps before the start line to allow the gradual acceleration zone to cover. Patients were asked to walk continuously and not to be concerned if there is a need to slow down or stop to rest.The total distance covered was divided by total time to calculate the fast speed. (cm/s)(10)The fast cadence (steps per minute) was calculated during the same 2MWT. The stride length was calculated by dividing the total distance covered by number of strides. (cm)(9)

After baseline measurement, subjects in both groups were given a similar conventional physiotherapy treatment and differences between the groups were made based on footwear insoles. Footwear of group A was modified by incorporating the Lateral Heel Wedged Insole along with medial arch support in it while the modifications for group B included Lateral Heel Wedged Insole alone. Both the assessors and the participants were blindfolded in the double-blind trial. Patients' masking was enabled by close-toed shoes since both groups receive the same conventional care. The subjects were given 24 weeks of treatment and outcomes for both groups were measured three times (after 8weeks, 16 weeks and 24 weeks). Some individuals lost to follow up so there were 55 participants left from which the results were concluded.

Data was analyzed by Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24. Demographic data was presented as mean \pm , and frequency while to find out the association offast cadence,fast speed and fast stride length with both group's treatment protocol were identifiedbyMultivariate Linear regression Test.Unstandardized beta coefficients with 95% confidence intervals were provided at the baseline 8th, 16th, and 24th weeks to aid in the interpretation of the data and to assist clarify the link between the two groups regarding fast cadence, fast stride length, and fast speed.

Intervention:

The following conventional physiotherapy treatment strategies were followed: To enhance range of motion, manual mobilization methods and muscle stretches were performed. Gentle workouts with moderate intensity and repeated motions to address muscle performance and neuromuscular control. enhancing balance by using balance training exercises as part of therapy Physical preparation, impact-free or low-impact aerobics. Both groups received these traditional exercises as first therapy.

The insoles used to modify footwear have the following traits:

Lateral heel wedged group

The study employed lateral heel wedged insoles, which were made of non-custom, high-density ethyl-vinyl acetate insoles dispersed bilaterally and preferably wrapped in leather. The insoles have a lateral wedge of 5 to 6 degrees.

Mediolateral wedged group

Full-length metatarsal support was provided by combining the medial arch support with the previously stated lateral heel wedged support.

RESULTS:

The mean age of all participant was 57.4 ± 3.7 years, the group A mean was 57.73 ± 4.04 years, meanwhile group b mean age was 58.57 ± 4.9 years. Total of $n=23$ (38%) participants were males and $n=37$ (62%) participants were females randomly allocated into two groups, where in group A the reported male were $n=10$ (33%) and females were 20 (67%). In group B the male were $n=13$ (43%) and females were $n=17$ (57%). Total of grade 2 osteoarthritis patients were $n=15$ (25%) and grade 3 OA patients were $n=45$ (75%). After randomization the patient allocated in group A diagnosed with grade 2 were $n=9$ (30%) and grade 3 patients were $n=21$ (70%), in group B the grade 2 patients were $n=6$ (20%) and grade 3 were $n=24$ (80%).

Fast cadence:

There was statistically significant improvement in fast cadence steps/min in 8th, 16th week and 24th week, reported as $F(4, 49) = 8.96$, $p < 0.0001$ Wilk's $\Lambda = 0.585$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.42$ from baseline 0 week.

Statistically, it is observed that for both the groups the baseline (0 week) fast cadence was with non-significant difference whereas fast cadence was improved in both the groups with statistically non-significant difference (equal improvement) at 8th week. Fast cadence at baseline was statistically reported as: group A mean 119 ± 3.81 , Group B mean 118 ± 3.2 $F(1, 52) = 0.70$, $p = 0.406$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.013$, and 8th week mean was: Group A 121 ± 4.3 , Group B 120 ± 3.7 $F(1, 52) = 0.77$, $p = 0.385$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.015$. The 16th week fast cadence was reported as: Group A 123 ± 4.8 and Group B 121 ± 4.3 $F(1, 52) = 4.65$, $p = 0.03$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.082$, meanwhile the fast cadence reported at 24th week as Group A 126 ± 5 Group B 122 ± 4.9 $F(1, 52) = 7.94$, $p = 0.007$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.133$.

Fast Speed:

There was statistically significant improvement observed in fast Speed cm/sec in 8th week, 16th week and 24th week, reported as $F(4, 50) = 9.8, p < 0.0001$ Wilk's $\Lambda = 0.576$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.42$

Statistically it is observed that fast speed was with statistically non-significant difference at baseline (0 week) and 8th week. Fast speed at baseline was statistically reported as: group A mean 123 ± 7.8 , Group B mean $122 \pm 6.5, F(1, 53) = 0.29, p = 0.59$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.005$, and at 8th week mean was: Group A = 130 ± 8.7 , Group B = $128 \pm 7.9, F(1, 53) = 1.70, p = 0.20$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.03$. The 16th week fast speed mean was reported as: Group A = 136 ± 9.6 and Group B $130 \pm 9.1, F(1, 53) = 5.20, p = 0.03$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.089$, meanwhile the fast speed reported after 24th week was: Group A = 141 ± 10 , Group B = $137 \pm 10.6, F(1, 53) = 7.43, p = 0.009$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.123$.

Fast Stride length:

There was statistically significant improvement in fast stride length (cm) in 8th week, 16th week and 24th week, reported as $F(4, 50) = 6.8, p < 0.0001$ Wilk's $\Lambda = 0.662$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.324$

Statistically it is observed that the 0-week, 8th week and 16th week fast stride length was with statistically non-significant difference (equal improvement), fast speed of 0 week was statistically reported as group A mean 124 ± 5.6 Group B mean $124 \pm 5.8, F(1, 53) = 0.02, p = 0.96$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.00$, and 8th week mean was Group

A 129 ± 4.9 , Group B 127 ± 6.2 $F(1, 53) = 0.96$, $p = 0.33$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.018$. The 16th week fast speed reported as Group A 131 ± 5.5 and Group B 129.1 ± 6.4 $F(1, 53) = 2.32$, $p = 0.013$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.042$, meanwhile the fast speed reported after 24th week as Group A 134 ± 6.2 Group B 132 ± 6.5 , $F(1, 53) = 3.72$, $p = 0.05$ with partial $\eta^2 = 0.066$.

Discussion:

The study was primarily conducted to find out the association of physical therapy combined with two types of footwear modifications regarding the improvement in spatiotemporal gait characteristics in patients with knee Osteoarthritis. Total 24 weeks treatment was completed, and gait parameters were measured at three different intervals. There was significant difference found between the two groups, with Medial Arch group showing more promising results. The findings of study showed that there was non-significant difference in fast cadence of two groups at baseline and also at 8th week with the increase of 2 steps per minute in both groups, while at 16th and 24th week, the fast cadence improved more significantly in Group A (2 and 3 steps respectively) as compared to group B (1 step per follow-up). The overall increase for medial arch group was about 7 steps per minute, whereas improvement was about 4 steps per minute for group with lateral wedge only. This increase in fast cadence was associated with a correction (decrease) of knee adduction load by both insoles, suggesting the lateral heel wedge insole decreased knee adduction less than the mediolateral heel wedge insole. A study supports the finding of this research as Every 1 step/minute increase in cadence was linked to a 0.02% drop in knee adduction moment angular impulse (11, 12) indicating that cadence is inversely connected with knee load when adjusting for gait speed. According to the average patient, for instance, an increase of 20 steps/minute in cadence would be associated with a decrease in knee adduction moment angular impulse of 0.4%, representing a 20% higher cadence, associated with a 25% lower knee adduction moment angular impulse. (11) Moreover, the effect of physical therapy on gait parameters has also been found to be significant. (6)

Statistically, it was proven in this study that the Fast speed was increased in all three intervals for both groups having significant correlation. The improvement in group A was recorded as more than group B with an increase in 7 cm/sec and 6 cm/sec after 8 weeks respectively. After the 16th week, the speed was increased as approximately 6 cm/sec for group A, and 2 cm/sec for group B. Meanwhile, after the 24th week, the speed added up 6 cm/sec and 3 cm/sec in both groups respectively. Overall improvement in the group A was 18 cm/sec while speed in group B improved by 11 cm/sec. This shows better results in patients using footwear with medial arch support. These findings are supported by a study which concluded that except for symptoms, lateral wedge insoles with different tilt angles were not any more successful at enhancing biomechanics or clinically significant results. (13) An evidence suggests that physical therapy induce healing factors with correction of biomechanics of the knee joint and the speed of the patient's fast walk is enhanced. In 2017, another study proposed that insole wedges increase speed in osteoarthritis patients, (14, 15) with a significant correlation with the biomechanical component of knee joint structure correction, namely, external knee adduction, (16) kinematics of knee joints, knee arm moments, ROM, knee adduction angular impulse, and ground reaction forces (17, 18)

There was also a significant difference found in fast stride length between both groups at 8th week (group A increased by 5 cm, whereas that of group B increased by 3 cm) but at 16th week, both groups showed similar improvements (2cm). After the 24th week, group A had a 3 cm increase in fast stride length while group B had a 1 cm improvement. Overall progress in group A was 10 cm and group B was 6 cm. In another study, it was shown that walking barefoot had the shortest stride length, which substantially differed from walking while wearing shoes with 0° and 5° insoles, and that walking while wearing shoes with 0° insoles had the longest stride length. The insole and foot interacted significantly as well. When walking barefoot in the OA group, a comparison within each group revealed a substantial difference in stride length between the affected and unaffected limbs. The OA group's stride length was significantly improved by wearing insoles. According to another study a significant difference exists between wearing shoes with 11° insoles and walking barefoot with osteoarthritis. As a result, when the OA stride length cadence and speed were measured with and without insoles, a significant variation in the opposite foot off's gait cycle between the affected and non-affected limbs was observed. (15) but at the same time, there is an extensive debate over the long term usage of lateral heel wedge alone as it does not decrease the knee adduction moment in long run due to the discomfort associated with its use. (8)

However, there are studies which show similar results to our study in terms of effects of physiotherapy treatment over the gait parameters. (6). However, here is a lack of evidence over the effect of different types of footwear modifications combined with physiotherapy on the spatiotemporal gait parameters specifically. So, the findings of this study will add more to evidence in this aspect.

Conclusion

There was significant association found between physical therapy intervention and both types of footwear modification in terms of improving spatiotemporal gait characteristics, but the statistics showed that the

pronounced results were found in medial arch group. The fast cadence, fast stride length and fast speed improved significantly in Group A. That is why the Lateral Heel Wedge with Medial Arch support is highly recommended for the correction of biomechanical function of knee joint which got disturbed after incidence of OA.

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References:

- Vincent KR, Conrad BP, Fregly BJ, Vincent HK. The pathophysiology of osteoarthritis: a mechanical perspective on the knee joint. *PM R*. 2012;4(5 Suppl):S3-9.
- Steultjens MP, Dekker J, van Baar ME, Oostendorp RA, Bijlsma JW. Range of joint motion and disability in patients with osteoarthritis of the knee or hip. *Rheumatology (Oxford)*. 2000;39(9):955-61.
- Gök H, Ergin S, Yavuzer G. Kinetic and kinematic characteristics of gait in patients with medial knee arthrosis. *Acta Orthop Scand*. 2002;73(6):647-52.
- Al-Zahrani KS, Bakheit AM. A study of the gait characteristics of patients with chronic osteoarthritis of the knee. *Disabil Rehabil*. 2002;24(5):275-80.
- Debi R, Mor A, Segal O, Segal G, Debbi E, Agar G, et al. Differences in gait patterns, pain, function and quality of life between males and females with knee osteoarthritis: a clinical trial. *BMC Musculoskelet Disord*. 2009;10:127.
- Fransen M, Crosbie J, Edmonds J. Physical therapy is effective for patients with osteoarthritis of the knee: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *J Rheumatol*. 2001;28(1):156-64.
- Abdallah AA, Radwan AY. Biomechanical changes accompanying unilateral and bilateral use of laterally wedged insoles with medial arch supports in patients with medial knee osteoarthritis. *Clin Biomech (Bristol, Avon)*. 2011;26(7):783-9.
- Nakajima K, Kakihana W, Nakagawa T, Mitomi H, Hikita A, Suzuki R, et al. Addition of an arch support improves the biomechanical effect of a laterally wedged insole. *Gait Posture*. 2009;29(2):208-13.
- O'Sullivan SB, Schmitz TJ, Fulk G. *Physical rehabilitation*: FA Davis; 2019.
- Bohannon RW, Wang Y-C, Gershon RC. Two-Minute Walk Test Performance by Adults 18 to 85 Years: Normative Values, Reliability, and Responsiveness. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*. 2015;96(3):472-7.
- Hart HF, Birmingham TB, Primeau CA, Pinto R, Leitch K, Giffin JR. Associations between cadence and knee loading in patients with knee osteoarthritis. *Arthritis Care Res*. 2021;73(11):1667-71.
- Shahine NF, El Ashri NI, Senna MK, Abd Elhameed SH. Effect of a pedometer based aerobic walking program on pain and function among elderly patients with knee osteoarthritis. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*. 2020;7(9):2020.
- Ferreira V, Machado L, Vilaça A, Xará-Leite F, Roriz P. Effects of tailored lateral wedge insoles on medial knee osteoarthritis based on biomechanical analysis: 12-week randomized controlled trial. *Clin Rehabil*. 2021;35(9):1235-46.
- Barati K, Ebrahimi Takamjani I, Shamsoddini A, Ejraei Dolatabad H. A comparison of the biomechanical and clinical effects of a biaxial ankle-foot orthosis and lateral wedge insole in individuals with medial knee osteoarthritis. *Disabil Rehabil*. 2022:1-8.
- Bijarchian MH, Majlesi M, Azadian E. Effectiveness of Increasing the Angle of Lateral Wedge Insole on Spatiotemporal Gait Parameters in Patients with Medial Knee Osteoarthritis. *Journal of Advanced Sport Technology*. 2020;4(2):19-28.
- Zafar AQ, Zamani R, Akrami M. The effectiveness of foot orthoses in the treatment of medial knee osteoarthritis: A systematic review. *Gait Posture*. 2020;76:238-51.
- Ferreira VMF. The effects of application of lateral wedge insoles on medial osteoarthritis of the knee. 2020.
- Kluge F, Krinner S, Lochmann M, Eskofier BM. Speed dependent effects of laterally wedged insoles on gait biomechanics in healthy.

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